

Exploration of the use of Project Based Learning (PBL) methodology in two accredited engineering programs at the Autonomous University of Yucatán

Miriam V. Chan-Pavón^{1,2}, Jesús F. Escalante-Eúan¹, Ileana C. Monsreal-Barrera¹, Carlos M. Rubio-Atoche¹

¹ Group of Production and Logistics Systems, School of Chemical Engineering, Autonomous University of Yucatan, Yucatan, México

² Estudiante de Doctorado en Informática, Universidad Americana de Europa, México-España.

Email: cpavon@correo.uady.mx, jesus.escalante@correo.uady.mx, ileana.monsreal@correo.uady.mx, carlosm.rubio@correo.uady.mx

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Abstract

The aim of this work was an exploratory qualitative investigation of the use of the PBL methodology in two currently accredited undergraduate programs at the Faculty of Chemical Engineering of the Autonomous University of Yucatan: Industrial Chemical Engineering (IQI) and Industrial Logistics Engineering (ILL). Project Based Learning (PBL) is considered today as one of the most effective methods in engineering education, because it allows students to develop competencies and skills that are increasingly demanded by organizations to new professionals and trainees. The methodology consisted of consulting the programs of the mentioned degrees and courses, in particular the didactic plans elaborated by the professors of each subject in order to select those that use project-based learning as an evaluation instrument. An exploration instrument was applied to students of the last semesters, with the purpose of knowing if this methodology is reaching its objectives and if the student has knowledge of the project-based learning methodology. The results showed that 72% of the curricula of the Industrial Logistics Engineering career apply this methodology (PBL) and 52% in Industrial Chemical Engineering. In conclusion, it was observed that a significant number of subjects in the undergraduate courses studied use project-based learning as a product for evaluating course performance; however, the PBL methodology is used empirically.

Keywords: Project Based Learning; Programs; Didactic plans; Accredited; Engineering.

1 Introduction

Traditionally, education has been fundamentally centered on teaching, and with it on the teacher as the axis of the teaching-learning process. Now, this change entails giving students a greater role, putting all efforts into their learning, relieving the role of the teacher to that of guide and orientor. Thus, the more behaviorist and cognitivist theories give way to constructivist theories, developing meaningful learning in students (Carrasco, Donoso, Duarte-Atoche, Hernández & López, 2015; Muñoz & Díaz, 2009; Navarro, Pertegal, Gil, González & Jimeno, 2011), in which the knowledge they already possess is integrated with the new knowledge they must acquire, making what they have learned last over time. It is not so important what the student knows at a given moment, but what he/she may come to know, which is closely related to his/her learning capacity (Estruch and Silva, 2006). More important than learning content is learning to learn, fostering continuous learning (Reverte, Gallego, Molina and Satorre, 2006; Taboada, Touriño and Doallo, 2010). Learning can be seen as a cumulative, self-regulated, directed, collaborative and individual process (Van den Bergh et al., 2006).

Project-based learning (PBL) appears to be an effective teaching method compared to traditional cognitive teaching strategies, particularly for the development of real-life problem-solving skills (Willard & Duffrin, 2003).

Project-based learning is a methodology that is developed in a collaborative manner that confronts students with situations that lead them to put forward proposals to address certain problems. By project we understand the set of activities articulated with each other, in order to generate products, services or understandings capable of solving problems or satisfying needs and concerns, considering the resources and time allocated. Authors and researchers who propose competency-based models in education consider that the project is an integrative strategy par excellence, and that it is the most appropriate to mobilize knowledge in situation (Díaz Barriga 2015; Jonnaert et. al. 2006). In this way, students can plan, implement and evaluate activities with purposes that have real-world application beyond the classroom.

Project-based learning has many benefits, among others, the possibility of continuous feedback and evaluation by the teacher, the establishment of a schedule of activities that show the progress of the different groups, generating a space for reflection by the student, preparing them for their professional and labor future, increasing motivation and involvement of both students and teachers. It increases their social and communication skills, improves problem solving and they learn to work in groups (Collazos, 2009). In addition, it promotes creative thinking and decision making, fostering higher academic performance. Bearing all the above in mind, it can be stated that PBL facilitates the learning of new knowledge and allows the application of the already acquired knowledge, develops transversal skills, including planning, writing, communication, as well as the responsibility to face a real situation (Carraco et al., 2015).

Nowadays, society requires an innovative engineer, bold in experimentation, with skills of interaction and exchange of ideas with other professionals from different areas (Duque & Martínez, 2000). This implies the establishment of a solid academic-cultural community, which breaks with the mental schemes that generate a presumed separation between scientific knowledge and humanistic knowledge. There is no point in training academic engineers who are alien to human sensitivity, just as there is no point in graduating artists without any hint of scientific rigor. Engineering is the conceptualization, design, construction and administration of projects and products aimed at providing a solution to a need of society or the environment. For this reason, the engineer must solve problems or provide different solutions, which requires imagination, creativity and synthesis of knowledge (Duque et al., 1999). Engineering, in general, is a decision-making process for the solution of problems within a particular field of action. This decision making involves different steps, among which the following stand out: delimiting the situation, proposing a solution strategy, obtaining experimental or theoretical information, analyzing the data and results, selecting the valuation criteria for the possible solutions, choosing the optimum variable and correcting the decision during its implementation (Garza-Rivera, 2001).

In response to the national and global needs of the integral formation of an engineer, capable of developing in the labor field, so that he develops skills and abilities to solve problems or provide different solutions, given this is why the Autonomous University of Yucatan (UADY), prioritizes the continuous professional training of students, through its educational programs taught in the Faculty of Chemical Engineering (FIQ), making use in recent years of the PBL methodology, as a method to obtain a competent learning for students who graduate and can perform satisfactorily in the labor field. Therefore, it is necessary to know and identify the results, effectiveness and contribution of the project-based learning methodology in the accredited programs of the faculty, taking as a sample the last semesters of the degrees of; Industrial Chemical Engineering and Industrial Logistics Engineering.

2 Objective

- Identify which subjects of the curriculum of each degree program declare in their didactic plans the use of the PBL methodology as an evaluation tool.
- Determine if students know the project-based learning methodology and if they have used it in any subject in order to know the impact and effectiveness it has had in the acquisition of new competencies for professional development.

3 Methodology

Considering that the research is qualitative and exploratory, it was established that the sample size for this exploration is 30 cases (Hernandez, Fernandez and Baptista, 2010), by degrees made up of eighth and tenth semester students, i.e. there will be 30 cases in total for students of the degree of Industrial Chemical Engineering and Industrial Logistics Engineering.

The first part of the research consisted of the exploration of the descriptive letters of the two accredited bachelor's degrees under study, which were consulted through the official website of the Faculty of Chemical Engineering of the UADY, which is shown in the following figure:

Figure 1. Portal de los planeaciones didácticas de los programas analizados

Subsequently, the results obtained from the descriptive charts consulted were compared with those found in the Moodle platform, which is used to support face-to-face classes by both teachers and students. On this platform, students can consult the guidelines for each of their subjects, including the topics, learning activities and the final evaluation method of the course.

The second part consisted of the application of a survey-type evaluation instrument using a Likert scale to the students to determine if they know and use project-based learning and how it impacts their training and the acquisition of skills.

The survey contains eight questions and was created using the Google Drive forms tool to make it easy to apply via email. Two important sources were used as a guide for the creation and adaptation of the evaluation survey (Carrasco, A., et al. (2015) and Rodríguez A., Río R, and Larrañaga J. (2016)). It should be noted that the exploratory research includes as a sample only students from the last two years of the degree.

3.1 Survey

1. ¿Have you heard of the Project-Based Learning (ABP or PBL) methodology?
 - Yes
 - No

2. Select the subjects in which you carried out a project in a real company:
 - for ILL students the possible options were:
 - Safety and industrial hygiene
 - Methods Engineering
 - Project management
 - Supply chain management systems
 - Warehouses and inventories
 - Formulation and evaluation of processes
 - Supplying
 - Marketing and customer service
 - Planning and control of operations
 - Strategic planning
 - for IQI students the possible options were:
 - Integrative project I
 - Integrative Project II

- Industrial engineering
 - Economic engineering
 - Process control
 - Service engineering
 - Process design
 - Process integration
 - Safety and industrial hygiene
 - Separations by continuous contact
 - Fundamentals of industrial engineering
3. ¿Mention if you have taken the (PBL) in subjects other than those selected above?
 - Open answer
 4. ¿Do you think that teamwork allows you to increase your motivation to learn or do you prefer to work individually?
 - Yes
 - No
 - I prefer work individually
 5. ¿Your teachers were available to give you support and help you solve any doubts about the project?
 - Totally agree
 - I agree
 - Neither agree nor disagree
 - Disagree
 - Strongly disagree
 6. ¿What do you think was the biggest obstacle you had to overcome to carry out a project of this type?
 - Communication skills
 - Time
 - Little access to the company
 - Unknowing of the objectives
 - Others
 7. ¿What kind of skills do you consider to have developed in the projects in which you were involved?
 - Leadership
 - Critical thinking
 - Autonomous learning
 - Conflict resolution
 - Collaboration
 - Creativity
 - Troubleshooting
 - Listen active
 8. ¿Do you feel that the projects are relevant to your professional future?
 - Totally agree
 - I agree
 - Neither agree nor disagree
 - Disagree
 - Strongly disagree

4 Results

4.1 Analysis of the didactic plans

Once the exploratory research was initiated, the descriptive letters and didactic plans of the five undergraduate courses offered by the School of Chemical Engineering were consulted, with the intention of finding out which subjects of their curricula declared the use of Project Based Learning, and the results were the following.

The first point was to determine the total percentage of the use of this methodology at a global level, that is to say, considering all the subjects taught in the five degree courses. It was found that 53% of the subjects contemplate the implementation of PBL within their descriptive charts, according to the figure below:

Figure 2. Overall percentage of subjects that reported using PBL as a learning technique..

Subsequently, of the total number of subjects that apply the PBL, the total percentage that corresponds to each degree program was explored, that is, out of a total of 123 subjects that apply this methodology to evaluate, the Industrial Logistics Engineering (IIL) degree program has 28%, resulting in the fact that, comparing all the degree programs, this is the one that applies this methodology the most, and Industrial Chemical Engineering (IQI), 21%, placing it in third place. This distribution is shown in the following figure:

Figure 3. Percentage of subjects that have reported using PBL as a learning technique, in each of the degree programs offered..

Taking these results into account, we proceeded to explore the undergraduate programs being evaluated, which are currently accredited by the faculty. Beginning with the analysis of the Industrial Logistics Engineering degree, the figure below shows the total percentage of use of this methodology by subject. This analysis shows that 72% of the subjects in its curriculum implement Project Based Learning. That is to say, 34 subjects state in their descriptive letters and didactic plans that they evaluate student learning through this study method, of the 47 that make up the curriculum.

Figure 4. Percentage of subjects that have reported using PBL as a learning technique in the Industrial Logistics Engineering plan.

In order to have a clearer idea of the distribution throughout the proposed training, the following graph shows the number of subjects that make use of it by semesters of the bachelor's degree under study.

Figure 5. Percentage of subjects that have reported using PBL as a learning technique in the Industrial Logistics Engineering plan, by semester.

Continuing with the analysis, we move on to the Industrial Chemical Engineering degree. In the figure below we can see that 52% of the subjects in its curriculum state that they implement this Project Based Learning methodology as an evaluation method. That is to say, out of its 50 mandatory subjects, 24 declare that they use this methodology.

Figure 6. Percentage of subjects that have reported using PBL as a learning technique in the Industrial Chemical Engineering plan.

In order to have a clearer picture of the distribution, the figure below shows the number of subjects that make use of the methodology (PBL) per semester, in the case of Industrial Chemical Engineering. It can be seen that the semester in which this evaluation method is most used is the eighth semester.

Figure 7. Percentage of subjects that have reported using PBL as a learning technique in the Industrial Chemical Engineering plan, by semester..

Once the results of the exploration of the descriptive letters and the didactic plans were obtained, the evaluation instruments were applied in order to measure their effectiveness and the impact they are having..

4.2 Analysis of student perceptions

Figure 3 shows the percentage of knowledge that students have in the use of this methodology. In the case of the students of the Logistics Industrial Engineering program (IIL), 58.9% know the PBL methodology, as well as 53.4% of the Chemical Engineering students (IQI).

¿Has escuchado hablar de la metodología de Aprendizaje Basado en Proyectos (ABP o PBL)?
56 respuestas

¿Has cursado alguna materia que utilice la metodología didáctica de Aprendizaje Basado en Proyectos (ABP o PBL)?
73 respuestas

Figure 8. Results of question 1 regarding knowledge of the methodology for IQI and IIL respectively.

The subjects that apply the PBL technique. For the Industrial Logistics Engineering (IIL) degree, Methods Engineering, Project Formulation and Evaluation and Supply stand out. For Industrial Chemical Engineering (IQI), none of the subjects presents a response that exceeds 50% as shown in the next figure.

Selecciona las asignaturas en las que llevaste a cabo un proyecto en una empresa real
56 respuestas

Selecciona las asignaturas en las que llevaste a cabo un proyecto en una empresa real
73 respuestas

IIL

IQI

Figure 9. Asignaturas que en sus planeaciones contemplan la técnica ABP y que los alumnos reportan haberla utilizado. IIL en azul e IQI en dorado.

According to the results presented in the next figure, more than 75%, in both careers, are convinced that teamwork motivates them to learn

¿Crees que el trabajo en equipo te permite aumentar tu motivación para aprender o prefieres trabajar individualmente?
56 respuestas

¿Crees que el trabajo en equipo te permite aumentar tu motivación para aprender o prefieres trabajar individualmente?
73 respuestas

IQI

IIL

Figure 10. Perception of students in relation to intrinsic motivation for teamwork.

The presence of the teacher with the students is necessary when using this technique. The accompaniment of the teacher provides certainty that translates into better achievement results. That was expressed by students from both programs.

¿Tus profesores estuvieron disponibles para brindarte apoyo y ayudarte a resolver las dudas del proyecto?
56 respuestas

IQI

¿Tus profesores estuvieron disponibles para brindarte apoyo y ayudarte a resolver las dudas del proyecto?
73 respuestas

IIL

Figure 11. Presence of teachers during the development of the project.

In the case of the challenges presented by the PBL technique (next figure) for the students of the Industrial Chemical Engineering program, the predominant factor is access to the company (53.6%) similar to the appreciation of the students of Logistics Industrial Engineering (58.9 %). On the other hand, for Chemical Engineers, the second factor that represents a challenge is communication skills (26.8%), which are the third factor for students of Logistics Industrial Engineering (11%) and vice versa, the third for IQI is the time factor (12.5%) which for IILs is the second element (24.7%).

¿Cuál crees que fue el más grande obstáculo que tuviste que vencer para realizar un proyecto de este tipo?
56 respuestas

IQI

¿Cuál crees que fue el más grande obstáculo que tuviste que vencer para realizar un proyecto de este tipo?
73 respuestas

IIL

Figure 12. Challenges to overcome in the elaboration of the Project

In relation to the skills developed during the development of the project, although they have different views, it is interesting to observe that they recognize the development of different skills as shown in the next figure.

¿Qué tipo de competencias consideras haber desarrollado en los proyectos en los que estuviste involucrado?
56 respuestas

IQI

¿Qué tipo de competencias consideras haber desarrollado en los proyectos en los que estuviste involucrado?
73 respuestas

IIL

Figure 13. Competences developed during the use of PBL as a learning method.

An important percentage (80.4%) of the IIL recognize that the development of projects as a learning technique is relevant for their professional future, while only half of the IQI students recognize this relationship.

¿Sientes que los proyectos son relevantes para tu futuro profesional?
56 respuestas

¿Sientes que los proyectos son relevantes para tu futuro profesional?
73 respuestas

Figure 14. Perception of the relationship between the skills developed and professional practice.

5 Conclusion

In general, we can conclude that the PBL technique is used as a learning model in the programs studied. From the results obtained we can establish that a greater use of the technique for the acquisition of knowledge is needed. As well as a more punctual presence of the teacher when this technique is proposed as a learning method.

In both study plans it is necessary to deepen the use of this technique and to integrate it in the last semesters so that learning has an even greater impact. It is necessary to reorient the strategies and deepen the research trying to discriminate those courses that use the methodology and those that remain superficial. This in order to be able to answer the question generated by the declared percentage of use of the technique versus the percentage of appreciation on the part of the students.

On the other hand, students recognize that the technique has an impact on several skills that will be useful during their professional practice. However, **it is not used in a systematized way by students or teachers**, in this work we only inquired with students who develop projects in real scenarios as part of the product of their subjects, but in an empirical way they actually apply it without the knowledge that there are a series of steps to follow.

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